

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The use of condoms to customers

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Abstract

Data from the Health Department of Riau until early 2014 quarter there were 132 new cases of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS). Pekanbaru tops the number of people with HIV and AIDS. The details of HIV cases and 76 56 AIDS cases cumulatively from 1997 until 2014 there were 2,388 cases of HIV and AIDS. The purpose of this research is to analyze the use of condoms to customers in the Jondul city of Pekanbaru by 2014. This research was qualitative research with the narrative approach gleaned from the results of the in-depth interviews on the main informant 4 persons ie customers and additional informants that "Mami" and sex workers. Data analysis was carried out with thematic analytical transcription, verification and the making of the matrix. The research showed that customers do not want the use of a condom during sexual intercourse to sex workers. Although sex workers have been trying to do deals to use condoms to customers but still no luck. The use of condoms to customers affected by perception, hassle and comfort in using those condoms. The City Health Office expects Soweto to conduct counseling regarding condom use, and required cooperation with local health professionals and NGOs in conducting coaching and training fitting condoms is good, correct and fast by sex workers to its customers.

Keywords: Customers; Use; Condom; HIV

1. Introduction

Health is an indicator to measure the level of welfare of a society or nation. The current healthy paradigm that is being promoted requires a change in people's mindset from treating disease to maintaining it

take care of your health so you don't get sick. Therefore, understanding about disease and how to prevent it needs to be disseminated to the public.

One aspect of health at the end of the 20th century which was a disaster for humans was the emergence of disease caused by a virus, namely HIV (Human Immunodeficiency Virus) which can cause AIDS (Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome). In this case, HIV and AIDS need special attention

The first case of AIDS was reported in 1981 in the United States. In 1983, HIV was isolated, which was later discovered to be the cause of AIDS. According to estimates by the United National Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (UNAIDS) or the UN Agency for AIDS control in 2012, the number of people living with HIV in the world has reached 35.3 million. Although the first case of AIDS was reported in the United States, currently most cases are found in Africa.¹

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), in 2011 there were 3.5 million people in Southeast Asia living with HIV and AIDS. Several countries such as Myanmar, Nepal and Thailand show a downward trend in new HIV infections. One of the reasons for this is the implementation of an HIV and AIDS prevention program through the 100% Condom Use (CUP) program. Trends in deaths caused by AIDS between 2001 and 2010 differed in each part of the country. In Eastern Europe

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and Central Asia the number of people affected by AIDS increased from 7,800 to 90,000, in the Middle East and North Africa it increased from 22,000 to 35,000, in East Asia it also increased from 24,000 to 56,000.¹

AIDS is often found abroad, but because relations between nations are becoming closer so that many foreigners come to Indonesia and many Indonesians go abroad for various purposes, this route opens up the possibility of AIDS transmission. The first AIDS sufferer in Indonesia was discovered in a male foreign tourist who died in Bali in April 1987.²

According to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) at the ASEAN level, HIV and AIDS in Indonesia is a sexually transmitted disease which is a health problem that must receive more serious attention by the government and all levels of Indonesian society. Indonesia is one of the countries in Asia that is experiencing an HIV and AIDS epidemic with prevalence increasing sharply and has not shown a decline even though efforts to overcome it have been implemented by the community, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and the private sector and government.²

AIDS in Indonesia is handled by the National AIDS Commission (KPA) and the National Family Planning Coordinating Board (BKKBN) and has a national AIDS control strategy for Indonesia. There are 79 priority areas where the AIDS epidemic is widespread. These areas are eight provinces, namely Papua, West Papua, North Sumatra, East Java, Jakarta, Riau Islands, Java and Central Java. AIDS control programs emphasize prevention through behavior change and complementing prevention efforts with treatment and care services.³

One of the government's responses related to overcoming the HIV and AIDS epidemic in Indonesia was the formation of the KPA through Presidential Decree No. 36/1994, followed by the release of the National Strategy for Overcoming HIV and AIDS in 1994, in line with the national strategy which suggested a partnership between the government and the community to overcome HIV and AIDS.³

Projections by the Indonesian Ministry of Health show that without accelerated HIV control programs, more than half a million people in Indonesia will be HIV positive in 2014. The epidemic is fueled primarily by sexual transmission and injection drug use. Papua, Jakarta and Bali occupy the top spots for new HIV cases per 100,000 people. Jakarta has the highest number of new cases, namely 4,012 cases in 2011. The basic factor causing this is because severe poverty amidst divergent patterns of rapid development, low levels of education and knowledge about HIV, gender discrimination, and sexual initiation at a young age.³

The development of HIV and AIDS in Indonesia in the third quarter (from July to September 2014) saw the number of HIV cases reported as many as 7,335 cases. The highest percentage of HIV infection was reported in the age group 25-49 years (69.1%), followed by the age group 20-24 years (17.2%) and the age group over 50 years (5.5%). Ratio of HIV cases between men and women. men and women are 1:1. The highest percentage of HIV risk factors is heterosexual risky sex (57%), Men Like Men (MSM) at 15%, use of non-sterile syringes among Injecting Narcotics Users (IDUs) at 4%. The number of AIDS cases from July to September 2014 reported only 176 AIDS cases. The highest percentage of AIDS was in the 30-39 age group at 42%, the 20-29 year age group at 36.9% and the 40-49 year age group at 13.1. The AIDS ratio between men and women is 2:1. The highest percentage of AIDS risk factors is risky sexual relations among heterosexuals at 67%, MSM (Men Like Men) at 6%, use of non-sterile syringes among IDUs at 6%, and from HIV positive mothers to children at 4%.⁴

The number of deaths due to AIDS in Indonesia is estimated at 5,500 people. The epidemic is mainly concentrated among intravenous drug users and their intimate partners, people involved in prostitution and their clients. In 2013 the number of people infected with HIV was 103,759 people, the number of people suffering from AIDS was 43,347 people, the number of deaths due to HIV and AIDS was 8,288 people. The number of people infected with HIV during January to March 2013 was 5,369 people, while the number of people infected with AIDS during January to March 2013 was 460 people.⁴

Data from the Riau Health Service, up to the beginning of the 2014 quarter, there were 132 new cases of Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) and Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS). Pekanbaru City is at the top of the list for the number of HIV and AIDS sufferers. The details are 76 HIV cases and 56 AIDS cases. Cumulatively from 1997 to 2014 there were 2,388 HIV and AIDS cases.⁵

The existence of Riau Province regional regulation no. 4/2006 concerning Prevention and Control of HIV and AIDS in Riau Province, is expected to be able to control the rate of the HIV and AIDS epidemic in Riau Province, including the increasingly developing city of Pekanbaru. Article 5 of the Regional Regulation states that preventing HIV and AIDS is carried out by: 1) Increasing faith and piety; 2) Do not have sexual relations outside of legal marriage; 3) Be loyal to

your regular partner and/or not engage in casual sex. This certainly will not work because it does not address the issue of the spread of HIV.⁶

One of the efforts that has been made to combat HIV and AIDS is the promotion of dual protection condoms as a contraceptive tool and to maintain sexual health, including preventing STIs and HIV and AIDS. The obstacle in using condoms while serving customers is that customers do not want to use condoms when having sexual relations with sex workers.⁷

Several research results show that the level of condom use among customers is still very low. In fact, using condoms during sexual intercourse is an important key to preventing HIV transmission because sexual intercourse is one of the main routes of HIV transmission. ⁷ Elliya's research results show that customers do not want to use condoms because they can reduce the pleasure of sex, and there are several perceptions that they suffer from STIs. their partner will not leave them and it will not result in death so they feel it is a normal thing and will recover even if they are not treated, and HIV and AIDS are cursed diseases so anyone will get it if it is destined by God. Apart from that, there is another perception that they are unable to refuse customers to have sex because they are afraid of being left by the customer, meaning they do not prioritize their health so they are unable to refuse the customer's request.⁸

Based on an initial survey conducted by researchers operating in the Jondul area in the Pekanbaru city area, the customers are mostly truck drivers, civil servants, school children and college students. Jondul is one of the names of a very popular area in Pekanbaru. Initially, Jondul was the name of a housing complex. However, now people are more familiar with Jondul as a place of prostitution. Jondul is in Tenayan Raya District, Pekanbaru City. At the time of the initial survey, some customers did not use condoms when having sexual relations with sex workers (PS) because customers assumed that it was useless to pay a lot of money if they had to use condoms, and it felt unpleasant, therefore some sex workers (PS) don't want to use condoms because they are afraid of losing customers and finally they have to obey the customer's wishes.

This shows that using condoms can prevent the spread of HIV and AIDS, so customers are expected to be able to use condoms when having sexual relations with those who are not their regular partners.

Based on the description above, it is not yet empirically known about the use of condoms among customers in the area. So the author is interested in seeing to what extent the use of condoms among customers can prevent the transmission of HIV and AIDS.

2. Literature review

No	Topics	Author/Year	Method	Results
1.	The influence of transgender characteristics on condom use among customers	Ridayanti D/2006	This research was applied with a qualitative approach	The research results showed that of 31 waria in Medan, only 1 waria always used condoms in their sexual activities. Likewise, according to the results of research by Rumaseuw on female sex workers in Wamena Regency, Irian Jaya, not a single sex worker used a condom when serving her customers.
2.	The influence of predisposing, supporting and reinforcing factors on the actions of commercial sex workers in using condoms to prevent HIV/AIDS in the Teleju localization, Pekanbaru City	Please RE/2015	This research was applied with a qualitative approach	The research results showed that 59.9% of sex workers agreed that customers should use condoms during sex, 68.5% of sex workers refused if customers did not use condoms during sex and 52.3% of sex workers agreed that using condoms would be better. feel safe. This means that sex workers know, are aware of the benefits of condoms and intend to use condoms.
3.	Bargaining ability of commercial sex workers in using condoms to prevent HIV/AIDS transmission on	Kenderwis, Ida Y/2010	This research was applied with a	Respondents responded to the assessment of the level of complexity of condoms in various ways, including: wearing them is very difficult, they are lazy to wear them, and

	the Sumatra Highway, Langkat Regency, North Sumatra Province		qualitative approach	customers feel their enjoyment is reduced. Refusal to use condoms by customers is understandable because the more complicated someone makes something, the greater the possibility that someone will refuse to use it.
4.	Factors related to consistent use of condoms among commercial sex workers (PSK) in the former South Belitung Bay scenic area of Bandarlampung	Elliya R/2012	This research was applied with a qualitative approach	that customers do not want to use condoms because it can reduce the pleasure of sex, and there are several perceptions that STI sufferers will not be left by their partners and will not result in death so they feel that it is normal and will be cured even if not treated, and HIV and AIDS are cursed diseases so that anyone will be affected if it is destined by God. Apart from that, there is another perception that they are unable to refuse customers to have sex because they are afraid of the customer leaving, meaning they do not prioritize their health so they are unable to refuse the customer's request.
5.	Support from WPS and customer friends for the use of condoms among WPS customers in Semampir Kediri	Kristianti S/2011	This research was applied with a qualitative approach	That customers do not want to use condoms because they are uncomfortable to use and are less practical, making it difficult for customers to use them

3. Research methods

The type of research carried out is qualitative with a narrative approach, namely an in-depth approach by continuously digging as deep as possible for information about the thoughts, feelings and desires that underlie certain behavior. 9 The research location was carried out in the Jondul area of Pekanbaru City, because it is still low use of condoms among customers at this location. The research started from the initial survey to the determination of the research, namely from June 2014 to January 2015. This research collected data from main informants, namely several customers according to adequacy and taken according to researchers who were believed to be able to provide accurate information in the Jondul area, Pekanbaru City. The additional informants are sex workers (PS) and "mom". Data analysis in this research uses transcription verification, thematic analysis and text and/or matrix creation.¹⁰

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Use of Condoms on Customers

One effort that can be made to prevent the transmission of HIV and AIDS from among sex workers is through the use of condoms. Condom use in Indonesia is still very low. The reason is because there are negative opinions in society and a lack of information about the correct use of condoms. Considering that using condoms can prevent the transmission of HIV and AIDS, it is hoped that sex workers can serve their customers so that they are willing and able to influence their customers to use condoms.

The use of condoms by customers is the most important thing in reducing the death rate, especially for the transmission of HIV and AIDS. Thailand has been successful in reducing HIV transmission rates by up to 83 percent with a condom provision program.

The results of research obtained in the Jondul area of Pekanbaru City regarding the use of condoms from the main informants, some said that they only occasionally used condoms and there were also those who said that they had only used condoms 2-3 times with sex workers. Apart from that, there are also those who say that they use condoms when asked by sex workers.

Based on research conducted by Ridayanti¹¹ on 31 waria in Medan, only 1 waria always uses condoms in their sexual activities. Likewise, according to the results of research by Rumaseuw¹² on female sex workers in Wamena Regency, Irian Jaya, not a single sex worker used a condom when serving her customers.

4.2. Customer Perceptions of Condom Use

There are several customer perceptions regarding choosing to use condoms. The main basis for choosing a condom always depends on the function of the condom and cannot be separated from the various types and functions.

Condoms not only prevent pregnancy, but also STIs including HIV and AIDS. Condoms are very effective if used properly and correctly. Condoms can be used with other contraceptives to prevent STIs.¹³

Condom use in Indonesia is still less than other countries such as Singapore, Malaysia, Bangladesh, America, Japan and Iran. Men's participation in supporting family planning using condoms is still low. In West Java only 1.7% of the 16,000 family planning participants. The reason is because there is a negative response from the public and a lack of information about the correct use of condoms. For example, this assumption is that family planning (KB) and reproductive health (KR) are women's affairs, men are rarely involved in health consultations, especially family planning.¹³

Around 70% of men think that it is better for their wives to participate in family planning. Apart from that, it is believed that condoms leak easily, are porous, thick, and taste bad during intercourse. This negative perception is increasingly becoming due to the lack of information regarding birth control methods for men.¹³

4.3. Customer Complexity in Condom Use

The level of condom use in this research location is still low, with the results of interviews with several key informants revealing that one of them only occasionally uses condoms. One of them stated that using a condom was complicated perhaps because he was not familiar with this contraceptive device.

Based on several factors, the reasons for the complexity of using condoms for sex worker clients include those who rarely put on condoms and also those who want to be quick and practical in having sexual relations. However, sex workers in principle want to fulfill customers' requests even though they have to not use condoms even though they already understand how to use condoms.

Based on this research, the information obtained from informants about the complexity of using condoms is that using condoms is a hassle/difficulty for customers to use. For this reason, there must be cooperation between related parties, including customers, sex workers and others, to provide information and counseling on how to use condoms properly so that there are no complications/difficulties in using condoms.

Research results from Keinderweis¹⁴ show that respondents responded to the level of complexity of condoms in various ways, including: wearing them is very difficult, they are lazy to wear them, and customers feel their enjoyment is reduced. Refusal to use condoms by customers is understandable because the more complicated someone makes something, the greater the possibility that someone will refuse to use it.

To overcome this condition, various efforts are needed to make it easier to use condoms, including conducting special training for sex workers and customers so that using condoms does not burden the customers as is done by sex workers in Thailand. Sex workers in Thailand have been able to put condoms on their customers quickly without their customers feeling burdened. This is supported by regulations in Thailand which require the use of condoms every time a sexual transaction occurs with someone who is at high risk of contracting HIV and AIDS or known as "No Condom No Sex".¹⁴

Based on the three factors that cause the complexity of using condoms for users of sexual services, including: usage technique, basic material factors, and habit factors, it turns out that the most determining factor is the habit factor. So it can be concluded that if someone is used to using something, then someone can be considered skilled so that other factors will not become complicated for them, as well as the complexity of using condoms.

4.4. Convenience in Using Condoms for Customers

There are several supporting factors to determine the customer's level of comfort in using condoms, including the practicality factor supported by the sex worker's service itself and also the enjoyment factor obtained by the customer. These two factors are variables that are more important than the previous 2 variables, namely regarding perception

and complexity in using condoms. Even though the comfort level variable is the main variable, without the support of the other two variables, it is difficult to draw conclusions from the results of this research.

From the research results obtained at the research location, in general, sex service users come to the location to get what they want, one of which is a high level of comfort at the location, both the surrounding environment and personal comfort. The two comfort level factors (practicality and enjoyment) are determining factors that cannot be separated from each other and are also the main factors in determining whether or not customers return to a location.

This is in accordance with the results of in-depth interviews by Kenderweis with sex worker customers, customers feel uncomfortable and unpleasant when using condoms, especially because they feel they have paid money to get this pleasure. 14

Overcoming this condition requires customer knowledge to know how important it is to use condoms. This can be done by sticking posters or brochures containing messages in each sex worker's room, or by placing leaflets on the table in the sex worker's room.

The existence of media such as posters, brochures or leaflets will make it easier for customers to know the dangers of not using condoms when having sexual relations with irregular partners, so that they no longer only think about momentary pleasure, but also about safety factors to prevent the transmission of HIV and AIDS.

Media is an intermediary or messenger from the sender to the recipient of the message. Efforts to display the message or information that the communicator wants to convey, so that the target's knowledge can increase and ultimately change behavior in a positive direction towards health.15

Convenience in using condoms is a convenience so that condom users can use them well. What is meant by comfort is that when having sex with a sex worker, the customer feels comfortable using a condom so that it does not cause discomfort for the customer. And to avoid discomfort, using a condom during sexual intercourse should not be used for a long period of time. 16

In essence, from several determining factors in influencing customers to use condoms, it turns out that the comfort factor, which includes pleasure, is the determining factor for mothers and sex workers to be able to look after customers.

4.5. Efforts Taken to Prevent the Transmission of HIV and AIDS

Nowadays, condoms, which are a long-known method of male contraception, are once again receiving new attention, both in the field of family planning and in other fields. The use of condoms will be quite effective if used appropriately and correctly. Failure to use condoms can be minimized by using condoms correctly, namely using them when the penis is erect and removing them after ejaculation. This contraceptive is the easiest to obtain and is not a hassle. Failure usually occurs when the condom breaks due to carelessness or due to pressure during ejaculation resulting in leakage. Condoms are effective for anyone. Allergy to condom rubber is very rare. 17

Pekanbaru City Health Service's HIV and AIDS prevention program requires regular counseling to PS. Health workers have provided counseling to PS but the level of condom use is still low. Based on NGO support related to PS' actions in using condoms, the process of providing information about the benefits of condoms and about HIV and AIDS includes individual approaches, observation and counseling.

4.6. Research Implications

In accordance with the findings in this research, the implication of these findings is that during the growth and development process, women need to be monitored throughout their life cycle using a life cycle approach. A life cycle approach means paying attention to the unique needs of handling the reproductive system and being sustainable towards this stage of the life cycle. Because women have special needs compared to men, women experience menstruation, pregnancy, childbirth, breastfeeding as well as menopause, women require more intensive care throughout their life cycle.

Reproductive health problems at each stage of the life cycle can be predicted and handled properly according to the needs of that stage, so that the possibility of negative consequences at the next stage of the life cycle can be prevented. The stages in a woman's life cycle are conception, infancy, child, adolescence, childbearing age and old age.

The first and second stages are mainly related to the health of the mother and newborn, the third stage is related to the health of adolescents. The fourth stage is related to family planning, and the fifth stage is related to late-life reproduction. All stages of this cycle are related to the prevention/control of sexually transmitted diseases (STDs/HIV and AIDS).

For this reason, preventing the transmission of HIV and AIDS is very important, especially through health education and increasing correct knowledge regarding the pathophysiology of HIV and how it is transmitted. In overcoming it, all efforts and activities are carried out, including prevention, treatment and rehabilitation activities. As is known, the HIV virus spreads through sexual relations with people who are not their regular partners.

In this case, if you have sex with multiple partners, it can cause sexually transmitted diseases that are not visible now, but a few years later the effects of this habitual behavior will be visible.

According to several informants, at the time of the interviews, it was not visually visible that they had any signs that they were currently infected with HIV and AIDS or other infectious diseases, because only by going to the laboratory could it be said that they had contracted the disease. If they have been infected with HIV and AIDS, it can be assumed that their reproductive health equipment is no longer good because it will cause the spread of the virus which can cause death. Apart from that, if pregnancy occurs, the transmission of HIV and AIDS from mother to child will have a direct impact on the child's disability.

For this reason, the reasons why customers still choose not to use condoms as protective equipment to avoid transmission of HIV and AIDS in Pekanbaru City should be used as consideration for the Government, Health Service and NGOs so that they can motivate sex workers and customers and "mammies" to gain knowledge regarding the transmission of HIV and AIDS and organizing outreach programs, especially for customers, sex workers and "mammies" about condoms, so as to reduce the transmission of HIV and AIDS in Pekanbaru City.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of research conducted using in-depth interviews regarding the use of condoms among customers in the Jondul area, Pekanbaru City, it can be concluded that condoms are rarely used by customers when having sexual relations with sex workers, due to the lack of customer awareness regarding preventing the transmission of HIV and AIDS. Customers' perception of condoms is good, but they still don't want to use condoms during sexual intercourse, because according to them it is not easy and complicated during sexual intercourse. Customers' comfort in using condoms also influences customers not to use condoms, because according to customers, if they use condoms, they feel uncomfortable.

The complexity of using condoms on customers also influences customers not to use condoms, making it difficult for them to avoid sexually transmitted diseases.

5.1. Suggestion

Based on the results of this research, the researcher provides suggestions, among others, namely that it is important for the Pekanbaru City Health Service or related parties to provide education to the Jondul area, especially customers, sex workers and "mothers" about the use of condoms for customers in order to anticipate the transmission of HIV and AIDS.

Collaboration with local health workers and NGOs is needed in providing regular and continuous guidance to sex workers as well as training on how to install condoms properly, correctly and quickly by sex workers to their customers. Apart from that, efforts to increase customer knowledge and also ensure that sex workers do not have difficulty convincing their customers about the importance of using condoms, this can be done by pasting posters or brochures containing the messages in question on the walls of rooms where prostitution occurs. Having outreach media in the room will make it easier for sex workers to convince their customers. This method is expected to increase the awareness of sex workers and their customers to use condoms, so that they no longer only think about comfort and momentary pleasure, but safety factors must also be considered.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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